

MICROWAVE ABSORPTION OF POLYPYRROLE SYNTHESIZED USING DIFFERENT OXIDANTS

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1. Introduction

Polypyrrole is a frequently studied conducting polymer due to its application in sensing and catalysis.[1] Polypyrrole is considered among the most promising conductive polymers due to its stability and ease of conversion between conducting and insulating forms.[2] Despite many interesting applications, the use of polypyrrole is limited because of difficulty in processing it. Several approaches have been explored to improve the ability to process polypyrrole, including the use of emulsion, inverse emulsion, steric stabilizer, and microemulsion methods. Several reports have also been published on the synthesis of polypyrrole-metal nanocomposites.[3] The sensing and catalytic abilities of the polypyrrole composites are significantly better than those for polymer alone.[4] As most of the important properties of the noble metals depend on their dispersion and surface properties in the surrounding medium, it is important to obtain evenly distributed Gold nanoparticles (GNPs) in conducting polymer matrix. Here we report a simple and convenient procedure for the synthesis of Polypyrrole (PPy) using HAuCl_4 and FeCl_3 as oxidants to obtain PPy-G and PPy-F polymer respectively. Both the polymers were characterized and studied for their micro-wave absorption properties.

2. Experimentals

2-1. Materials All the chemicals used in this study were ACS reagents. Pyrrole (99%), gold (III) chloride trihydrate ($\text{HAuCl}_4 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 99.0%) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich and used as-received

without further purification. Deionized water was used in the experiments.

2-2. Preparation of PPy-G and PPy-F polymers 0.03 M of distilled pyrrole was added to the solution of 0.06 M oxidant solution and the reaction mixture was stirred continuously at 0 ~ 5 °C to obtain PPy-G and PPy-F polymer. The obtained product was filtered and washed thoroughly with methanol (CH_3OH) and the sample was dried under vacuum for more than 24 h at room temperature.

2-3. Characterization The FT-IR spectra of the samples were measured by a Perkin Elmer (model 783) IR spectrometer in KBr medium at room temperature. The UV-vis spectra were recorded by a Shimadzu UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (UV-3101PC) in chloroform. The morphology of the synthesized composite films was investigated by SEM (COXEM-CX100s) and TEM (JEM-2000, JEOL, Japan). XRD patterns were recorded using a D8 Advance (Bruker) X-ray diffractometer with Cu K radiation ($\lambda = 1.5418 \text{ \AA}$). The microwave-absorbing characteristics were evaluated by measuring the reflection loss by an HP scalar spectrum analyzer, and the sample sheets (180 mm × 180 mm × 2 mm) were mounted onto an aluminum substrate, the sheets were prepared by using conventional painting technique. The prepared samples were evaluated by reflectivity measurements using the waveguide technique in a frequency range of 2 to 10 GHz. To guarantee precision of the measurements, the used setup was prepared with components presenting high mechanical precision [4].

3. Results and Discussion

In Fig. 1(a) the IR spectra of both PPy-F and PPy-G indicates absorption peaks corresponding to the bipolaron bands were observed at 1220 and 910 cm^{-1} , in good agreement with spectroscopic

characterization of PPy [2,3]. The shift in position of the peak at 1560 cm^{-1} , corresponding to $-\text{C}-\text{N}$ stretch to higher wave numbers in the spectra, indicates an effective charge transfer between the GNPs and PPy. In the figure 1(b) UV-Vis spectra of PPy-G clearly shows a broad peak of around 436 nm indicates the presence of GNPs. To confirm the presence of GNPs in the polymer PPy-G, the XRD spectra was analyzed which is as shown in Fig. 1(c). The peaks due to (112), (200) (220) and (211) are the Bragg reflections of GNPs can be clearly observed in all the samples suggesting the formation of PPy-G. The TEM images in Fig. 2 suggest the formation of fiber like structures in PPy-G and granular/spherical particles for PPy-F. The structure of PPy-G also contains some spherical particles embedded in the fiber structures are the GNPs surrounded by PPy particles. From both SEM and TEM images the particles size of both PPy-G and PPy-F are $\sim 25\text{-}35$ and $30\text{-}40$ nm respectively. Figure 3 shows the experimental results of reflection loss versus frequency for PPy-F and PPy-G polymers in the range of 2– 10 GHz. PPy-F shows a weak wave-absorbing ability which is in the range 10-20 dB and the peak position of the absorption moves slightly higher as the frequency increased. The absorption ability increases for PPy-G peak increases is in the range 20-21 dB and the peak position of the absorption remains more or less same as the frequency increased.

Fig. 1 (a) FTIR, (b) UV-Vis spectra, and (c) XRD patterns for PPy-F and PPy-G polymers.

Fig. 2. TEM and SEM images for PPy-F and PPy-G polymers.

Fig. 3. Reflection losses for the polymers PPy-F and PPy-G.

4. References

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